

Relationship between Collaborative Learning and University students' Attitudes towards Learning English: Insights from Pakistani Instructors

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ABSTRACT

Collaborative Learning (CL) ensures educational and interpersonal benefits for Pakistani university students. Therefore, research in prospects of CL in learning English as a Second Language (ESL) at Govt. university level is insufficient. This research aimed at investigating the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and its relationship with their prospects about university students' attitudes towards learning English via sociocultural theory. Pakistani ESL instructors from 7 various English departments of 7 public universities were selected employing cluster sampling. Adapted questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from 35 Pakistani ESL instructors. Research revealed that the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors were moderate and high about their university students on the basic five elements of CL in learning English. Likewise, Pakistani ESL instructors revealed high prospects about their university students on three aspects of attitudes towards learning English. A weak positive correlation between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and their prospects about the attitudes of their university students towards learning English was reported. Pakistani ESL instructors revealed that university students gain academic and social benefits through CL activities i.e. lessening fear and anxiety, maintaining social relations, activating participation, enhancing communication, solving problems, and achieving higher order thinking skills. This attempt is beneficial for instructors, parents, policy-makers, curriculum designers, and researchers to promote the excellence in university students' collaboration.

Keywords: Attitudes; collaborative learning; English as a second language; sociocultural theory.

INTRODUCTION

English is the medium of instruction in Pakistan as an Asian country (Khan et al., 2023). Collaboration skills are essential for students to develop because they function as tools in life (Suharti et al., 2024; Maghfiroh et al., 2024). Collaborative Learning (CL) is appreciated as a novel teaching

English approach in English as a Second Language (ESL) context (Khan & Mansoor, 2020). It ensures practical, holistic, and communicative skills in the process of learning English (Qureshi et al., 2021). Sociocultural theory (SCT) of Vygotsky (1978) supported this approach because its main stance deals with the interaction of a senior member with other members of the class to help them out to reach at their potential levels in learning English. This term was devised by Bruffee (1993) and it got fame later on in other parts of the world (Chatterjee, 2015; Manasia, 2020). Additionally, it has established a distinct position for itself in the field of pedagogies by depending on its five fundamental components, which include interpersonal skills, positive interdependence, individual and group accountability, group processing, and face-to-face supportive contact in the acquisition of English (Chatterjee & Correia, 2020; Davidson & Major, 2014; Johnson & Johnson, 2017; Laal & Laal, 2012; Yu et al., 2022). Therefore, CL helps university students to learn and perform different activities together in the form of small groups to complete the fixed tasks, solve the problems, and accomplish particular objectives (Khan et al., 2023). On the other hand, three aspects of attitudes such as affective, cognitive, and behavioural in learning English of Pakistani university students help to achieve goals. Pakistani instructors expressed that students could not properly communicate in English classes (Khan & Mansoor, 2020).

Few factors are the cause of poor performance of students that affect learning English i.e., lack of effective policies (Qureshi et al., 2021), untrained instructors (Haidar & Fang, 2019), out-dated curriculum (Manan et al., 2017), traditional teaching approach (Khan et al., 2023), higher strength in classes (Panhwar, 2016; Yasmin & Naseem, 2019), less interest (Yasmin & Sohail, 2018), and product oriented classrooms (Khan et al., 2023). Students' attitudes assure the failure and success in learning English (Gardner, 2014). Some barriers are reported in CL environment by instructors, for instance, size of group and teaching practice (Baker & Clark, 2010). There are also other factors that are illustrated by instructors in learning English using CL i.e., designing groups (Le et al., 2018), similar and different groupings, uneven participation of group members and big classrooms (Kanika et al., 2022). Li and Campbell (2008) and Scager et al. (2016) stated that improper usage of communicative and collaborative skills are the root causes of students' failure in learning English via CL.

Additionally, social loafing is also another problem in the way of CL (Popov et al., 2012). Similarly, work division in small groups is highlighted by instructors as one of the critical phases in CL (Gillies, 2010; Lagat & Concepcion, 2022). Gillies & Boyle (2010) disclosed that assessment of students in small groups and handling class timings limit students' learning in CL. Furthermore, anxiety and fear in small group work may hinder the successful learning of students in CL (Abrami et al., 2004). And Le et al. (2018) stated that insincere performances of learners also restricted English learning via CL. This research aimed at investigating the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and its relationship with their prospects about university students' attitudes towards learning English. The aim of research of research is divided into three further objectives as follows; (a) To investigate the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL in learning English, (b) To investigate the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English, (c) To determine the relationship between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and their university students' attitudes towards learning English.

Few research attempts have been made to investigate the perspectives of university students using CL towards learning English but research about CL and attitudes as a mutual attempt from the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students is still lacking (Khan et al., 2023; Qureshi et al., 2021). The previous research studies emphasised on the effects of maths, economics, social studies, engineering, and science students in learning English employing CL (Gillies & Boyle, 2010; Yasmin & Naseem, 2019) at beginner, middle, and advance educational levels in numerous contexts including Europe, America, Australia, and Asia (Le et al., 2018). Yasmin and Naseem (2019) recommended that CL is at its early stage in Pakistani higher education institutions (HEIs). The qualitative research approaches specified that Pakistani university students like holistic learning in groups (Afzal, 2020). Quantitative research needs to

be investigated on the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors using CL about their students in Pakistan (Rasool & Winke, 2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. CL

CL is a teaching approach that emphasises cooperating to accomplish group goals. Students make a sincere effort to look for outcomes from collaborative tasks that benefit every participant of the team proportionately (Sener & Mede, 2022). In its broadest sense, CL is an educational strategy meant to optimise both individual and group members' performance (Johnson & Johnson, 2017; Othman & Murad, 2015). CL gives students an avenue to collaborate in order to accomplish their desired outcomes (Laal & Ghodsi, 2012). Furthermore, Laal (2013) contends that while CL fosters beneficial interdependence in ESL classrooms—a crucial component that produces better results over the long term—teacher-oriented ESL classrooms typically limit the learning of learners in an organised setting for immediate benefits. Furthermore, CL has expanded its function in the most recent approaches to teaching English. As a result, the prospects of ESL instructors are regarded as a crucial component of English language instruction worldwide.

Similar to this, in order for all public and private universities to achieve the requirements for an excellent and exceptional educational experience, the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan likewise concentrated on the necessity of engaging and novel learning techniques as CL (Ghazzoul, 2018). CL is a cutting-edge approach for imparting English that increases students' enthusiasm, drive, and self-assurance while reducing their tension, anxiety, and fear of the language (Yasmin & Naseem, 2019). The collaboration of ESL instructors with students and students' interaction with other fellows are observed as critical and serious aspects in learning English (Shamim & Rashid, 2019). The concepts of interaction and collaboration among group members are emphasised in English language classrooms (Kanika et al., 2022). The small group work creates the environment of interaction in English language classrooms which is the essence of CL classrooms. Okolie et al. (2021) recommend that collaborative tasks help learners to learn English at the best of their efforts through social interaction. In addition, CL is considered an effective method of teaching because it equally encourages the learners, motivates them for active learning, and improves their critical, social, communicative, and decision-making skills (Khan et al., 2023).

Adesina et al. (2022) investigated the effect of peer evaluation on learners' engagement in group work. The qualitative survey was used to collect data from 165 first year university students of England. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data and the results revealed that group work fostered engagement and learning. Qureshi et al. (2021) carried out research on the impact of social factors on CL, engagement, and performance of university students via constructivist theory. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyse the collected data through questionnaire. The study revealed that social factors i.e., peers' interaction, social presence, the use of social media impacted CL settings, engagement, and performance of students. Okolie et al. (2021) looked into a research that aimed to investigate the effect of CL activities to enhance university students' engagement in acquiring practical skills. 250 Nigerian university students participated in the study. Through Hayes-PROCESS Macro 3.5, the mediation analysis was conducted. The findings based on regression analysis suggested that CL activities influenced greatly the engagement of students in acquiring practical skills.

Kanika et al. (2022) conducted a recent study on the impact of homogenous and heterogeneous groups on students' performance and experience of learning in CL environment. Groups improved students' performance and experience. Specifically, heterogeneous groups performed far better than homogeneous group in performance whereas homogenous group students expressed better experiences as compared to heterogeneous group. Sühendan and Bengü (2014) examined the attitudes of learners (166) studying in preparatory school from diverse faculties towards CL through focus groups. The results claimed positive and negative attitudes of students about CL. CL is widely practised across the world because of its multiple

advantages over teacher-centred pedagogy e.g., it engages students in practical activities, enables them to solve problems, develops their motivation, confidence, and thinking skills, reduces their fear and anxiety, enhances their interactive, social, and communicative skills in learning English (Gonzales & Torres, 2016; Neo et al., 2012).

b. Attitudes

Gardner (2004) explained attitudes' definition through Likert perspective as "the sum total of a man's instincts and feelings, prejudice or bias, preconceived notions, fears, threats, and convictions about any specified topic" (p. 267). Ajzan (2005) reflects attitudes as "a disposition to respond favourably or unfavourably to an object, person, institution, or event" (p. 4). Similarly, Gardner (2004) added that "motivation refers to the combination of effort plus desire to achieve the goal of learning the language plus favourable attitudes toward learning the language" (p. 10). Whereas Wenden (1991) argues that attitude comprises three aspects named as affective (emotions and feelings), cognitive (ideas, opinions, and beliefs), and behavioural (actions) towards an object. Nguyen (2022) and Kara (2022) proposed a meticulous connection among these three aspects. As such, attitudes play crucial role as they influence either students' success or failure in their learning of English (Getie, 2020).

Eshghinejad (2016) queried about the attitudes of Iranian learners towards learning of English. The statistical investigation showed that learners hold generally positive attitudes about learning the English language. Likewise, Al-Samadani and Ibnian (2015) conducted a study on the effect of attitudes of Saudi learners (112) on their academic achievement towards learning English. The results of the study confirmed that learners have positive attitudes towards learning English. Tahaineh and Dana (2013) investigated the female Jordanian learners' attitudes (184) towards learning English. Female learners demonstrated positive attitudes towards English language learning. Al-Noursi (2013) also discovered United Arab Emirates (UAE) learners' attitudes (196) towards learning English. Learners showed positive attitudes towards learning English. Ming et al. (2011) inspected the attitudes of Malaysian secondary school learners about learning English. The research respondents verified positive attitudes towards learning English. In addition, learners of science showed greater interest in learning English than the Art learners. Abidin et al. (2012) finalised a research work on the attitudes of Libyan students (180) towards learning English. 180 participants were enrolled in three various fields of sciences like life, social, and basic. The contributors illustrated negative attitudes towards learning English. The female learners' attitudes were slightly better as compared to the male students' attitudes.

c. Sociocultural Theory

From a philosophical standpoint, CL and SCT are related (Lantolf et al., 2018). Holzman (2016) claimed that Vygotsky established and transformed SCT for ESL teachers and students in a variety of ways. Vygotsky contends that emphasising acquiring information is just one aspect of SCT's viewpoint, additionally arguing that evaluating students' problem-solving skills is crucial. According to Lantolf et al. (2018), ESL teachers largely initiate education using SCT. SCT is a huge asset to the all-encompassing ESL acquiring context. It also takes into account the idea that mastering ESL might be viewed as a beneficial achievement rather than an unprocessed procedure. For ESL students to communicate and work together in ESL, SCT offers a trustworthy environment (Xu & Zhang, 2019). Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) ensures that students actually experience intercultural expansion, while SCT emphasises engagement as an intricate approach for the advancement of pupils' effectiveness in ESL settings (Novita et al., 2020). ZPD is a highly well-known Vygotskian concept pertaining to CL (Lantolf et al., 2018). Vygotsky asserts that if the projects are correctly guided by the More Knowledge Other (MKO) acting comme an intermediary, pupils can finish them with no apprehension. Additionally, ZPD addresses how students' cognitive growth is a result of their

social milieu's interpersonal interaction, which is an integral part of their everyday lives (Lagat & Concepcion, 2022).

Engagement in an interpersonal context produces the creation of information (Lagat & Concepcion, 2022). Additionally, cultural relationships influence how mental processes manifest. For the students to achieve their personal self-regulation, they must grow in ZPD. ZPD, according to Gul et al. (2022), is the difference between pupils' existing and possible growth capabilities with a focus on educational environments. At that stage, the person's achievement in words is defined as their real expansion stage, while their possible growth stage describes the communication effects that they generate when collaborating with teachers, classmates, and additional pupils (Şener & Mede, 2022). University students participate in the completion of assignments with their mature colleagues when they interact and collaborate alongside them (Vygotsky, 1978). This setting makes it easier for each learner to integrate into the neighbourhood and complete real-world tasks by having conversations with other participants (Zhang et al., 2022). Thus, when students positively impact their community and their surroundings about them, their cognitive growth will occur (Khan et al., 2023). ZPD holds that social norms bring life to primordial understanding rather than it emerging from the mind on its own. According to Lagat & Concepcion (2022), an ESL instructor helps students improve their interpersonal and verbal skills by acting as an advisor and collaborator in the classroom.

METHODS

Although it relates to the impartial investigation for obtaining trustworthy, genuine, and legitimate conclusions from the information gathered, a survey-based framework for quantitative study method is used for this goal (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). Furthermore, quantitative data assures researchers with genuine outcomes (Bryman, 2016; Tashakkori et al., 2020). In other words, the findings of research from statistical data via questionnaires withdraw complete, compact, accurate, and authentic insights about the research topic (Bryman, 2016; Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Pakistani ESL instructors from seven English departments of govt. universities from Islamabad participated in this research. These ESL instructors were teaching English to university students of English departments. Total numbers of 35 Pakistani ESL instructors were chosen randomly from different 7 govt. universities, for instance, five ESL instructors from each university. Out of 35 instructors, 21 research participants with 60 percentages were males and 14 with 40 percentages were females. These ESL instructors were aged from 31 to 50 years old.

A modified survey with 35 items on a 5-point Likert scale to elicit responses focused on the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors regarding their university students in CL, i.e., interpersonal skills, individual and group accountability, positive interdependence, group processing, and face-to-face promotional interaction. According to Khan et al. (2023), these items had an alpha value of 0.942 ($\alpha=0.942$), which guarantees exceptional dependability. These 35 questionnaire's items were selected from the published research work (Abrami et al., 2004; Alhabeedi, 2015; AlMashjari, 2013; Buchs et al., 2017; Duckworth, 2010; Er & Aksu Atac, 2014; Farzaneh & Nejadansari, 2014; Gonzales & Torres, 2016; Ingleton et al., 2000; Neo et al., 2012; Titsankaew, 2015; Xuan, 2015).

The adapted questionnaire on the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about three aspects of attitudes i.e., affective, cognitive, and behavioural of their university students towards learning English comprised on 25 items based on a five point Likert scale with an alpha value of 0.966 ($\alpha=0.966$) that acknowledged excellent reliability (Khan et al., 2023). This questionnaire was adapted through selecting different items from the past research (Abidin et al., 2012; Abu-Snoubar, 2017; Alkaff, 2013; Al-Noursi, 2017; Al-Samadani & Ibnian, 2015; Al-Tamimi & Shuib, 2009; Asghar et al., 2018; Colaste, 2018; Eshghinejad, 2016; Gardner, 2004; Ibnian, 2017; Kashefian-Naeeni et al., 2018; Ming et al., 2011; Naqeep & Zaued, 2014; Razy & Amer, 2016; Soomro et al., 2018; Tahaineh & Dana, 2013; Vo, 2017; Zuo et al., 2019).

The chairpersons of seven government institutions' English departments allowed the investigators to conduct their study. In addition, a signed written consent was received from all the research participants who showed their interest to participate voluntarily. Research participants were guided clearly about the major aim and objectives of this research. Research participants were handed over questionnaires and they filled questionnaires in almost 20-25 minutes.

Gathered data on the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English were analysed via applying descriptive statistics such as mean and standard Deviation. For determining the relationship between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English, inferential statistics in the form of Pearson correlation was applied. Table 1 indicates the interpretation of insights and prospects through mean score.

Table 1. Interpretation of the Mean Score

Mean	Agreement Level	Prospects Level
4.5 - 5.0	Strong Agreement	Very High
3.5 - 4.49	Agreement	High
2.5 - 3.49	Neutral	Moderate
1.5 - 2.49	Disagreement	Low
1 - 1.5	Strong Disagreement	Very Low

Abu-Bader (2021) categorised Prospects into mean score from five various perspectives i.e., very low, low, moderate, high, very high. 4.5 to 5 mean score means very high, 3.5 to 4.49 mean score is known as high, 2.5 to 3.49 mean score is considered moderate, 1.5 to 2.49 mean score is declared as low, and 1.00 to 1.5 is categorised as very low as shown in Table 1.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This research aimed to investigate the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and the prospects of Pakistani ESL teachers about their university students' attitudes towards learning English.

Table 2. Insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about students in CL in learning English

Elements with Statements of CLA	D		
Positive Interdependence	5	.11	32
CL enables my students to make decisions in English class.	5	.40	55
CL enables my students to think critically in English class.	5	.34	68
CL enables my students to solve problems in English class.	5	.31	67
My students want to be with their friends in CL in English class.	5	.60	55
My students do not want to be with their friends in CL in English class.	5	.88	86
CL enables my students to help each other in English class.	5	.48	56

CL enables others to help my students in English class.	5	.45	56
CL enhances my students' connection with peers in English class.	5	.45	56
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Individual and Group Accountability	5	.49	58
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CL creates relaxed learning atmosphere in English class.	5	.48	56
CL reduces my students' anxiety in English class.	5	.48	56
CL reduces my students' fear in English class.	5	.45	56
CL makes my students' learning of English easier.	5	.51	56
CL enhances my students' abilities to complete the tasks on time in English class.	5	.48	56
CL enhances my students' abilities to do quality work in English class.	5	.51	56
CL enhances my students' performance in English assessments/tests.	5	.54	56
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Group Processing	5	.59	50
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My students choose their group members in CL in English class.	5	.60	77
I assign students in groups in CL in English class.	5	.54	50
I assign groups of similar abilities in CL in English class.	5	.31	90
I assign groups of mix abilities in CL in English class.	5	.74	44
I assign group members seated near each other in CL in English class.	5	.91	98
CL enables my students to negotiate in English class.	5	.40	55
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Social and Interpersonal Skills	5	.41	53
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I assign groups of similar abilities in CL in English class.	5	.31	90
CL enhances my students' listening proficiency in English class.	5	.42	55
CL in English class enhances my students' English speaking proficiency.	5	.42	55
CL in English class enhances my students' English reading proficiency.	5	.42	55
CL in English class enhances my students' English writing proficiency.	5	.42	55
CL in English class enhances my students' communication skills.	5	.40	55

Face to Face Promotive Interaction	5	.44	53
CL enables my students to express opinions in English class.	5	.48	56
CL enables my students to argue in English class.	5	.51	56
CL enables my students to debate in English class.	5	.48	56
CL enables my students to negotiate in English class.	5	.40	55
CL enables my students to ask questions in English class.	5	.40	55
My students choose their group members in CL in English class.	5	.60	77
CL enhances my students' interest in English class.	5	.34	80
CL enhances my students' motivation in English class.	5	.45	56
Total Items	5	.20	.03

Table 2 displays insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL in learning English. The results illustrate that the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors were almost high about their university students on the basic five elements of CL such as positive interdependence (M=4.11), individual and group accountability (M=4.49), group processing (M=3.59), social skills (M=4.41), and face to face promotive interaction (M=4.44) in learning English because the mean score was higher than 3.50. So, Pakistani instructors' Prospects were high. The overall mean score of instructors is reported as high (M=4.20) that means Pakistani university students support CL environment for learning English.

Previous studies on CL showed that the basic elements of CL helped students to learn English in better way through CL as a sociocultural phenomenon (Qureshi et al., 2021). Similarly, Neo et al. (2012) had found very high Prospects about CL elements i.e. Positive interaction (M=3.70 to 4.0), individual and group accountability (M=3.25 to 3.50), face to face promotive interaction (M=3.87 to 4.02), social skills (M=3.83 to 4.11) and group processing (M=3.77 to 4.06). In addition, Gonzales and Torres (2016) also explored high Prospects on five elements of CL i.e., Positive interaction (M=3.43 to 3.47), individual and group accountability (M=3.81 to 4.00), face to face promotive interaction (M=3.21 to 3.47), social skills (M=3.32 to 3.51) and group processing (M=3.38 to 3.44). These findings are similar to the past studies (Abrami et al., 2004; Alhabeedi, 2015; AlMashjari, 2013; Buchs et al., 2017; Chen, 2005; Farzaneh & Nejadansari, 2014; Ingleton et al., 2000; Liu, 2015; Titsankaew, 2015; Xuan, 2015).

Instructors overall expressed high Prospects on positive interdependence. On the basis of data, instructors favoured positive interdependence because it helped their university students to assist each other in solving problems. Almost all instructors who participated in this study were happy about the success of the group (M=4.08). Thus, based on these results, it could be said that the learners had a positive outlook towards the idea of positive interdependence in CL. These findings are similar to Gonzales and Torres (2016), and Neo et al. (2012). Instructors also showed high Prospects about individual and group accountability. Instructors supported CL and they endorsed CL for positive participation, knowledge sharing, and listening ideas. Apart from being very motivated, almost all the students in the CL group were aware of their roles in the group (M=4.40). From this, it could be said that the learners responded positively towards CL when it comes to individual and group accountability. These findings reflect that of Johnson and Johnson (2017), Gonzales and

Torres (2016), and Neo et al. (2012) who also stated the same results for individual and group accountability. Instructors showed high Prospects on social skills because it was easy for them to share ideas, work, and communicate properly in the groups.

ESL university students respected each other's opinions in communication and therefore, they showed positive responses on social skills. These findings are also similar to the studies of Johnson and Johnson (2017), Gonzales and Torres (2016), and Neo et al. (2012). University students expressed high Prospects on face to face promotive interaction. They appreciated face to face promotive interaction because it provided a base for the understanding of the subject matters and lessons with the improvement of performance. High Prospects also directed that ESL university students took good decisions in groups. Johnson and Johnson (2017), Gonzales and Torres (2016), and Neo et al. (2012) claimed the same results for face to face promotive interaction. Instructors supported the element of group processing via showing moderate Prospects since it enhanced cooperation in group members, helped them to achieve goals, and enabled them to enjoy working in groups. Instructors anticipated positive responses about group processing like the studies of Johnson and Johnson (2017), Gonzales and Torres (2016), and Neo et al. (2012).

Table 3. Prospects of ESL instructors about students' attitudes towards learning English

Aspects of Attitude	D		
Affective Aspect	5	.73	60
Learning English makes my students feel confident.	5	.65	48
Learning English makes my students feel proud of them.	5	.68	47
Learning English makes my students happy.	5	.60	49
Learning English is interesting for my students.	5	.88	32
Learning English is useful for my students.	5	.91	28
Learning English is good for the self-development of my students.	5	.68	47
Cognitive Aspect	5	.56	83
My students like reading books in English.	5	.45	50
My students like reading newspapers in English.	5	.45	50
My students like reading magazines in English.	5	.40	49
My students like reading Journals in English.	5	.42	50
My students like reading stories in English.	5	.65	48
My students like reading poems in English.	5	.62	49
My students like watching TV shows in English.	5	.54	50

My students like watching movies in English.	5	.65	48
My students like listening to songs in English.	5	.62	49
My students like watching news in English.	5	.45	50
My students like learning English.	5	.85	35
Learning English increases the knowledge of my students.	5	.65	48
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Behavioural Aspect	5	.72	52
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Learning English is necessary for my students to communicate with others.	5	.85	35
Learning English helps my students make friends.	5	.65	48
Learning English helps my students travel abroad.	5	.54	50
Learning English helps my students pursue higher studies.	5	.80	40
Learning English opens up more job opportunities for my students.	5	.62	49
Learning English is important for the career of my students.	5	.62	49
Learning English helps my students use modern technology (Internet, Social Media/Facebook, Twitter).	5	.94	23
Total number of items	5	.45	.15

Table 3 displays the results of the prospects of Pakistani instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English. The results showed high prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about the attitudes of their university students towards learning English. The attitudes were explored on the basis of three aspects like affective ($M=4.73$), cognitive ($M=4.56$), and behavioural ($M=4.72$) and their prospects are interpreted as high. It means that Pakistani ESL instructors expressed supportive prospects about their university students towards learning English. Previous studies revealed similar findings (Abidin et al., 2012; Al-Noursi, 2017; Al-Tamimi & Shuib, 2009; Asghar et al., 2018; Colaste, 2018; Eshghinejad, 2016; Ming et al., 2011; Naqeeq & Zaued, 2014; Razy & Amer, 2016; Zuo et al., 2019) in their specific contexts.

Instructors expressed very high Prospects on affective domain of attitudes towards learning English because it enhanced the feelings of university students towards learning English and the results are similar to past studies (Abidin et al., 2012; Alkaff, 2013; Al-Samadani & Ibnian, 2015; Eshghinejad, 2016). High Prospects were revealed by ESL instructors on the cognitive domain of attitudes towards learning English since it helped them to develop their thinking skills. These findings are similar to the past research (Asghar et al., 2018; Colaste, 2018; Eshghinejad, 2016; Kashefian-Naeeni et al., 2018; Naqeeq & Zaued, 2014). High Prospects were revealed by instructors on behavioural aspects of attitudes towards learning English. Similar results were also declared by the past research work (Razy & Amer, 2016; Soomro et al., 2018; Tahaineh & Dana, 2013; Vo, 2017; Zuo et al., 2019).

Table 3. Relationship between the insights of ESL instructors about students in CL and attitudes towards learning English

		L	s	Attitude
Insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	5		
Prospects of Pakistani ESL Instructors about their university students' attitudes	Pearson Correlation	021		1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	903		
	N	5		35

Table 4 determined the relationship between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and the prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English. However, weak positive correlation ($r=.021$) was determined between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and prospects of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students' attitudes towards learning English. A weak positive correlation between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and their prospects about university students' attitudes towards learning English was determined. On the contrary, these results are different from the conducted research of Gonzales & Torres (2016) and Neo et al. (2012). On the other hand, Lagat and Concepcion (2022) also measured the relationship in three various paradigms such as CL, perceived learning, and social interaction. Therefore, significant positive correlation was reported between CL and social interaction.

These findings add to the emerging discussion of the effectiveness of CL on students' attitudes toward learning English and corresponds to the emphasis that sociocultural theory places on the interactive and social features of language learning proposed by Vygotsky, cited in Holisman 2016. Above average to high insights by Pakistani ESL instructors on the five essential elements of CL represent the theoretical underpinning of positive interdependence and mutual support highlighted by Johnson and Johnson (2017). The findings correspond to the statement made by Laal and Ghodsi (2012) that collaborative activities enhance interpersonal skills and academic success. However, the weak positive correlation between CL and the attitudes of students reflects a complex relationship that may, in turn, be interfered with by external influences such as instructors' facilitation skills (Gillies & Boyle, 2010), institutional support (Buchs et al., 2017), and socio-economic contexts around Pakistani universities (Haidar & Fang, 2019). While instructors perceive that CL reduces anxiety and enhances communication, its potential to significantly impact attitude change may require targeted interventions as suggested by findings from Farzaneh and Nejadansari (2014) on cooperative learning for reading comprehension.

Current study also highlighted dual benefits and challenges of the implementation of CL in public universities in Pakistan. While CL enhances social engagement and problem-solving skills, its limited impact on attitudes toward English may indicate that deeper motivational or cultural barriers might be at play (Rasool & Winke, 2019). These barriers align with the findings of Panhwar (2016), who highlighted the importance of culturally responsive pedagogical frameworks for enhancing the efficacy of CL. Furthermore, implications of the study also go along with Chatterjee and Correia's (2020) emphasis on developing a sense of community within collaborative settings in an effort to enhance the students' general experience. The teachers' assessment of the effectiveness of CL verifies research by Afzal (2020) and Khan et al. (2023), adding to the call for policy-makers and curriculum designers to incorporate reflective and adaptive CL strategies. Moreover, further research should investigate the longitudinal impact of CL, and, as Abrami et al. (2004) highlight, explore what contribution training programs for teachers are making to bridge the gap between instructional insights and actual attitude changes.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to investigate the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and its relationship with their prospects about university students' attitudes towards learning English. Pakistani ESL instructors showed high insights about their university students on the basic five elements of CL and also high prospects on three aspects of attitudes towards learning English. Besides, a weak positive correlation between the insights of Pakistani ESL instructors about their university students in CL and their prospects about university students' attitudes towards learning English was reported. The significance of SCT in Pakistani university systems was recognised in this investigation. This study project has specific restrictions as well. This study focused on the perspectives of Pakistani ESL instructors regarding their university students in CL and their expectations regarding the attitudes of university students towards learning English. Data from 35 instructors who were randomly chosen from the English language departments of 7 government universities in Islamabad was gathered using the cluster sampling technique. Finally, this study used a quantitative questionnaire-based investigation approach. Comparable studies can be carried out in both domestic and foreign settings at private institutions and universities. Future studies may examine the attitudes of Pakistani university students towards studying English and the likelihood that they will use CL. Additionally, researchers might look into the perspectives of Pakistani teachers regarding the difficulties their university students in CL have when learning English. The relationship between Pakistani private university instructors' perceptions of their students' attitudes towards studying English and their insights regarding their students' use of CL must be ascertained.

Declaration of conflicting interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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